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Promotion in the Australian Public Service: Improvements for women and stagnation for cultural and linguistic minorities

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Promotion in the Australian Public Service: Improvements for women and stagnation for cultural and linguistic minorities

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Key findings

We use the universe of personnel records to examine promotion prospects in the Australian Public Service (APS) by gender and by three Equal Employment Opportunity groups—people with a disability, Indigenous Australians and people from non-English speaking backgrounds (NESB).

- Over the 2001-2020 period, women and members of the three EEO groups are less likely to be promoted at almost all APS levels compared to their counterparts, but the results are most stark for NESB staff.
- Promotion prospects for women improved dramatically from 2012. In recent years, women are more likely to be promoted than similar men at the higher levels of the APS.
- NESB promotion prospects have deteriorated over time and poor NESB promotion prospects are not explained away by language or cultural factors. Our analysis is suggestive of a promotion penalty for either looking or being different or non-white.

What we knew

- Australia is a highly successful multicultural country with half its population either first or second generation migrants.
- This diversity is not reflected in the APS leadership where NESB individuals hold only 6.5 per cent of SES positions despite having representation of around 15 per cent overall in the APS.
- Affirmative action strategies and APS-wide policies have been implemented for the APS for women (2012/2013), Indigenous Australians (2015) and people with a disability (2012 and 2016).
- Our paper summarises the large literature on promotion in the US Civil Service and field experiments and empirical papers on discrimination in Australia.

What we do

- We use the APS Employment Database (APSED) covering 2001-2020.
- We observe people's public service careers and important demographic information.
- We estimate logit models of the probability of promotion (and separation) conditional on all observable characteristics.
- We control for gender, membership in one of the EEO groups, APS graduate experience, central agency experience, education, and a qualification in economics, finance or accounting. We further control for spells on leave, part-time work, time within the service and at current level and year fixed effects in all of our estimates.
- We define as NESB any employee with the following characteristics:
 - COB not Australia and first language is not English; or

Figure 1: Promotion and EEO characteristics

Source: APSED. Estimated Regression Coefficients. Bars represent 95% confidence interval.

Note: “1” indicates equal probability of promotion. Numbers greater (less) than one indicate higher (lower) probability of promotion for first-listed group. Bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

- COB Australia, first language not English and either mother’s or father’s first language not English; or
- COB Australia or overseas, first language is “English” or “English and another language” and both parents’ first language is not English.
- We compare conditional promotion prospects for women and members of the three EEO groups against others. We present these as relative promotion prospects as in Figure 1

What we know now

- From Figure 1 we see that there are promotion penalties for women and all EEO groups at nearly all levels. The promotion penalty for NESB gets larger at higher levels.
- From Figure 2 we see that NESB individuals who were born in Australia or who arrived before the age of 6 still suffer a large (and growing at higher levels) promotion penalty. These NESB individuals speak fluent English and are culturally Australian, but still face a promotion penalty.
- In the main paper (Figure 7), we show that Asian NESB face larger penalties than non-Asian NESB and that this is even true for English speaking Asians. This is suggestive of a penalty for “looking different.”
- From Figure 3 we see a dramatic improvement in promotion prospects for women which coincides with the APS-wide gender equity policies introduced in 2012 and 2013.
- From Figure 4 we see that promotion prospects for NESB have not improved over time, but seem to have worsened somewhat. We find no differences between NESB men and women.

What this means for policy

- The experience of women suggests that focused policy attention can overcome promotion barriers. If anything, the APS now appears to over-promote women relative to similar men.
- Improving prospects for NESB individuals likely requires focused policy attention.

Figure 2: Promotion by Australian born/raised and NESB status

Figure 3: Female promotion relative to males: changes over time

Figure 4: NESB promotion relative to ESB: changes over time

Caveats and future research directions

There are several notable caveats to our results, all of which provide opportunity for future research to extend these results.

1. We do not observe who applies for promotion. If NESB individuals are not applying for promotion the policy actions are different than if NESB individuals are applying for promotion but being denied. We are unable to say anything about the mechanism that generates the observed promotion patterns.
2. We do not observe any data on individual performance. Information on individual performance reviews would provide useful, additional information to help understand what impacts the observed patterns.
3. Other mechanisms such as tokenism, access to informal networks, mentorship opportunities or unconscious bias may all be present in explaining our results. Our quantitative approach does not allow us to test these mechanisms.

Where to now?

In response to our research, the APS has been responsive by announcing a [Culturally and Linguistically Diverse Action Plan 2025-2028](#).

It will be interesting to track the effectiveness of this plan going forward.

Our data is now available in the ABS secure Datalab and can be linked to economy-wide datasets. Using this linkage, additional research examining the employment and income outcomes of EEO group members who leave the public service would be a useful complement to the work that we have done in this paper.

More information

- Get the [Working paper](#) or the [Full published paper](#).
- We would welcome the opportunity to present our research to your team and to discuss potential joint research projects on related or similar topics.
- Contact us at robert.breunig@anu.edu.au